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CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: In today's changing world, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is a growing area of interest for academics, practitioners and entrepreneurs, in terms of both theory and practice. The discussion about Sustainable Development (SD) and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has risen above average and a huge amount of different terms have been established. Corporate activities are increasingly regarded as a necessary part of the network of organizations involved in creating social infrastructure or addressing social issues. A framework is presented in which the relationship between SD and CSR is defined to ease further research in SD and CSR, moreover, to enhance the development of new methodologies and instruments towards the implementation of SD / CSR strategies into companies.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Corporate Social Responsibility, Corporate Sustainability

INTRODUCTION

A Greek Playwright coined the word "*Philanthropy*", 2500 years ago. And while terms like "*giving*", "*corporate social responsibility*", "*sustainability*", have become popular in the business lexicon, the underlying thought for all of those is one "*a love for humanity and work for healthy planet*".

The corporate and private sector is crucial for any country and region's inclusive, equitable and sustainable

growth, contributing to regional cooperation and economic progress by bringing investments, expanding market, generating employment, creating infrastructure, wealth and global competence. The ongoing globalization, trade, commerce and dynamics of a fast moving economy have also transformed the role and responsibilities of the business fraternity, which is now influencing future economic trends, carbon-footprints, environmental and social dimension and Govt. policies through and within its Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) landscape. **Sustainability** refers to an organization's activities, typically considered voluntary, that demonstrate the inclusion of social and environmental concerns in business operations and in interactions with stakeholders.

To understand and enhance current efforts, the most socially responsible organizations continue to revise their short and long-term agendas, to stay ahead of rapidly changing challenges. The quality of relationships that a company has with its employees and other key stakeholders "such as customers, investors, suppliers, public and governmental officials, activists, and communities" is crucial to its success, as is its ability to respond to competitive conditions and corporate social responsibility (CSR).

Corporate responsibility or sustainability is therefore a prominent feature of the business and society literature, addressing

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) refers to operating a business in a manner that accounts for the social and environmental impact created by the business. CSR means a commitment to developing policies that integrate responsible practices into daily business operations, and to reporting on progress made toward implementing these practices.

Common CSR policies include:

- Adoption of internal controls reform ;
- Commitment to diversity in hiring employees and barring discrimination;
- Management teams that view employees as assets rather than costs;
- High performance workplaces that integrate the views of line employees into decision-making processes;
- Adoption of operating policies that exceed compliance with social and environmental laws;
- Advanced resource productivity, focused on the use of natural resources in a more productive, efficient and profitable fashion (such as recycled content and product recycling); and
- Taking responsibility for conditions under which goods are produced directly or by contract employees domestically or abroad.

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) strategy, based on sound ethics and core values, offers clear business benefits. Sustainable development rests on three fundamental pillars: economic growth, ecological balance, and social progress.

Sustainability and CSR

Emphasis on social environmental and economic sustainability has become a focus of many CSR efforts. Sustainability was originally viewed in terms of preserving the earth's resources. In 1987, the World Commission on Environment and Development published a landmark action plan for environmental sustainability. The commission, named after former Norwegian Prime Minister Gro Harlem Brundlandt, defined sustainability as "meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs." Companies are now challenged by stakeholders including customers, employees, investors and activists to develop a blueprint for how they will sustain economic prosperity while taking care of their employees and the environment.

At the same time, mainstream investors are being challenged to ensure that they review CSR issues when analyzing companies. The United Nations Environment Program Financial Initiative asked one of the world's largest law firms to research whether institutional investors such as pension funds and insurance companies are legally permitted to integrate environmental, social and governance issues into their investment decision-making and ownership practices. The resulting report, released in October 2005, concluded that investors were not only permitted to but also sometimes required to take such factors into account. "Integrating environment, social and governance considerations into an investment analysis so as to more reliably predict financial performance is clearly permissible and is arguably required in all jurisdictions," the report concluded.

Sustainable Development

The origin of the term SD lies in the 18th century and was actually used in forestry. In those times, it was only allowed to cut down a certain number of trees so that a long-lasting protection of the tree population was guaranteed. This method ensured a continuous supply of wood without reducing resources for forthcoming generations. The Club of Rome precipitated an international discussion due to its report "Limits to Growth" (Meadows, 1972). In the course of this discussion, an eco-development approach was created which effected the protection of resources and environment coming to the fore. This development has led to the mission statement of SD we have today. In 1987, the World Commission on Environment and Development defined SD as an ethical concept and has become the major definition of SD: "Sustainable Development is a development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. It contains within it two key concepts: the concepts of "needs", in particular the essential needs of the world's poor, to which overriding priority should be given; and the idea of limitations imposed by the state of technology and social organisation of the environments ability to meet present and future needs. Thus the goals of economic and social development must be defined in terms of sustainability in all countries developed or developing, market-oriented or centrally planned." cited in "Our Common Future" (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). Elkington goes more into detail when arguing that companies should not only focus on enhancing its

value through maximizing profit and outcome but concentrate on environmental and social issues equally" (Elkington, 1998). Therefore SD is defined as a model of triple-bottom-line.

CORPORATE RESPONSIBILITY

Whereas the term SD has mainly started to be used in the 1980's, the framework of CSR has already been established in the 1950's and 60's. Bowen defined CSR in 1953 - as one of the first as "...an obligation to pursue policies to make decisions and to follow lines of action which are compatible with the objectives and values of society" (Douglas et al., 2004). In the beginning, however, the term Social Responsibility was rather used than CSR. Social Responsibility assumes that economic and legal duties of the companies should be extended by certain responsibilities to society (McGuire, 1963). Carroll argues that Social Responsibility exists of four components such as economic, legal, ethical and discretionary expectations that society has of a company and that companies have to decide which layer they focus on (Carroll, 1979).

On the other hand, Friedman "as most known defender of the neoclassical view of economics" defines Social Responsibility completely differently: "There is one and only one social responsibility of business - to use its resources and engage in activities to increase its profits so long as it stays within the rules of the game, which is to say, engages in open and free competition, without deception or fraud" (Friedman, 1962). Until today this neoclassical view has been the primary paradigm of business. Concepts of SD and CSR criticize this point of view. As Wood puts

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Organizations such as the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) actively take part in the sustainability and CSR discussion. WBCSD regards CSR as engine for the social dimension (social progress) which supports companies to fulfill their responsibilities as good citizens and defines CSR as "business' commitment to contribute to sustainable economic development, working with employees, their families, the local community, and society at large to improve their quality of life (WBCSD, 2006). On the other hand, the Commission of European Communities describes CSR as a "concept, whereby companies integrate social and environmental concerns into their business operations and interactions with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis (Commission of the European Communities, 2001).

Relation between CSR & Sustainable Development

CSR is an integral part of sustainable development. Exactly where it fits in is vigorously debated, mainly because the concept of sustainable development also has many different interpretations. This diagram, illuminates CSR's relationship with sustainable development.

Fig.1 : Relationship between SD and CSR.

The basic idea to incorporate the sustainability aspect into business management should be grounded in the ethical belief of give and take to maintain a successful company in the long-term. As the company is embedded in a complex system of interdependences in- and outside the firm, this maintaining character should be fulfilled due to the company's commitment in protecting the environment or reducing its ecological footprint and due to the general acceptance of its corporate behaviour by society in- and outside of the firm.

It is recommended that CSR is to be used as social strand of the SD-concept which is mainly built on a sound stakeholder approach. CSR focus especially on the corporate engagement realizing its responsibilities as a member of society and meeting the expectations of all stakeholders. The figure below shows the proposed framework in which SD is defined by Brundtland and the model of the triple-bottom-line as an ethical concept which offers ideas concerning sustainable orientation on a macro-level.

Fig. 2: Relationship between SD, Corporate Sustainability and CSR.

The concept of SD on a corporate level is stated as Corporate Sustainability which is based on the three pillars economic, ecological and social issues, therefore, the social dimension is named CSR. The corporate orientation on sustainability is specially affected by external influences due to the specific sustainability orientation on a macro-level:

- Legal/Institutional: laws, human rights, etc.
- Technological: new technologies
- Market: suppliers, competitors, customers, trends
- Societal: NGO's, society
- Cultural: attitudes, behavior
- Environmental: nature, availability of resources

Not only does society influence the company, the implementation of Corporate Sustainability in companies also has positive effects on society in the long-term, as indicated by the grey columns which reach into the white area of figure.

CSR is about Company Core value

According to the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) report for Corporate Social Responsibility; Issues which have emerged strongly from the work group are as follows:

Human Rights:

Human Rights are the universal rights that every person is entitled to enjoy and to have protected. The underlying idea of such rights "fundamental principles that should be respected in the treatment of all men, women and children" exists in some form in all cultures and societies.

Such rights are enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted by the United Nations in 1948. The declaration covers two broad sets of rights: Civil and Political Rights; and Social and Cultural Rights.

Stakeholder Rights:

There is no argument that shareholders who own the company have the first call on the performance of management. But some argue that companies also have to satisfy a broader group of interested parties, commonly called stakeholders. These include not only shareholders, but also employees, customers/consumers, suppliers, communities and legislators. Such stakeholders are seen to have both influence and rights, which although different in kind and degree from those of shareholders, still demand respect.

Employee Rights:

Employee rights are embodied in the International Labour Organization's Declaration on the Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work. These include: freedom of association and the right to collective bargaining; elimination of all forms of forced and compulsory labor; abolition of all child labor; and the elimination of discrimination in respect of employment and occupation.

Environmental Protection:

Protecting the environment from the impact of operations is a core

International Journal of Management and Economics responsibility. Besides their legal obligations, which differ according to region and country, corporations are seen to have a broad responsibility to protect the physical environment throughout their supply chains. They should commit to continuous improvements in eco-efficiency (doing more with less) and managing the full lifecycle of their product or service.

Community Involvement:

Community issues cover a broad range of activities, including community assistance programs; supporting educational needs; fostering a shared vision of a corporation's role in the community; ensuring community health and safety; sponsorship; enabling employees to do voluntary work in the community; philanthropic giving.

Supplier Relations:

Supply chains are mostly complex interrelationships between a wide range of companies. Corporations can be – and are – affected by the actions of their direct and indirect suppliers. They can inherit the consequences of bad practices of those higher up the chain, such as the use of child labor and polluting production methods.

Monitoring and assessing:

Effective management of CSR demands monitoring, measuring and reporting of performance against generally accepted indicators. The systems to achieve this are still in their infancy, but much can be learned from those developed over the past decade for the management, monitoring and reporting of environmental impacts and performance. This includes systems that can be independently verified.

Objective of the Study

Over the last decades, sustainability has become very popular in modern economics. All terms such as CSR, Corporate Citizenship, Corporate Sustainability or Social Responsibility seem to go in the same direction: the prime objective is to find out where the focus in the sustainability discussion is and how the terms SD and CSR are defined.

Research Methodology: Secondary Data from the literature studied concerning CSR and Sustainable Development.

CONCLUSION

According to the emergent literature, there is a growing awareness that business needs to manage its relationship with the wider society. Corporate leaders are responsible for their corporations' impact on society and the natural environment beyond legal compliance and the liability of individuals. More experienced leaders can gain new perspectives on how to grow in their approach to sustainability and how to develop innovative business models. CSR is becoming a leading principle of top management and of entrepreneurs.

CEOs have long been accountable to a varied group of stakeholders – employees and communities, as well as investors. The nature of these relationships is now changing in ways that significantly affect corporate performance.

In part due to the emergence of the Internet and continuing globalization, companies are becoming accountable for labor issues and working conditions in their partners' operations as well as their own.

Organizations can reexamine their behaviors and begin their journey toward a sustainable approach that is integrated into their business strategy. And thus for CSR

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and sustainable development, companies
must:

1. Align and incorporate CSR with business strategy and integrate it across all operational functions. Thus, making it easy to invest (not spend) the funds necessary to achieve its objectives.
2. Implement an open information strategy for more transparent information-sharing with multiple stakeholders.
3. Leverage transparency to increase the level of engagement of key constituents and customers.

When these activities are done in combination, CSR can become a dimension of a company's successful competitive strategy. Done right, it offers a company improved relationships with all of its key constituents, more loyal customers, lower costs, higher revenues and an overall improvement of the business standing in society.

References

- Tripathi PC and Reddy PN (2006). Principles of Management, Tata McGraw Hill, New Delhi: 41.
- Kotler Philip, Corporate Social Responsibility.
- Werther & Chandler, Strategic Corporate Social Responsibility.
- World Commission on Environment and Development (1987). Our Common Future. The Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- WBCSD (2006). Corporate Social Responsibility. <http://www.wbcsd.org>
- George Pohle and Jeff Hittner: Attaining sustainable growth through corporate social responsibility.

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<http://www.greenearthalliance.in/node/16>
www.google.com
www.wikipedia.com

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